

Students' Attitudes to Teachers' Code -Switching at Undergraduate Level in Pakistan

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Abstract *The study investigates attitudes of social and natural science students towards the practice of code switching by respective teachers at undergraduate level. For this purpose, Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT) is applied. An adapted questionnaire of El-Fiki (1999) focused the advantages, disadvantages and CS practice as a helping tool in teaching methodology. The statistical results show a variation in the students' attitudes based on gender, program and academic background. Furthermore, the results show that the students favor CS as it enhances the comprehension level of the students regarding the subject, they are enrolled in. The study concludes that teachers' code-switching proves helpful in achieving the academic goals.*

Introduction

Communication is a two-way process that helps both listener and speaker to comprehend the message behind the words. According to Bakhtin (2010), communication occurs between two conscious minds while both minds are aware of the language that is used in the discourse. Therefore, communication in another language helps the speaker to deal with certain issues. Consequently, with the communication issues speakers usually adopt different techniques to make the communication process easier and effective.

Code Switching is basically defined as switching to sounds, words, phrases or sentences of other language to the native language of the listener to make the communication process effective (Gumpers, 1982). However, to perform all other activities, there is a need to practice other languages. English language is

acceptable as an international language around the world. Moreover, it is widely practiced as a medium of communication in academic setting.

Pakistan considered among those countries where English language is an official language. Therefore, it is necessary to learn and use it fluently for keeping good socio-economical relationships. On the other hand, the focus of learning English is to achieve excellence in academic career. In order to achieve a good academic career, it is essential to learn and speak English with accuracy and fluency in Pakistan. It not only helps the students to perform better in educational institutes but also keeps them motivated to act confidently in real life situations (Imran & Ghani, 2014).

In the Pakistani context, students are exposed to Urdu in order to communicate in a real-life situation nationally. However, educational institutes want to make every student capable of communicating internationally. The use of these two languages together is termed as CS or CM. The features of these two terms considered as among oral practice of language. The current study aims at investigating undergraduate students' attitudes regarding teachers' code-switching inside the classroom.

Literature Review

Code-Switching (CS) is explained as the discontinuous use of more than one language which helps in creating a communicative and social meaning (Auer, 2013). It is necessary to focus on both the "codes" from two different languages which are used by the speaker. CS is a process which involves only those speakers who have good command on any of two different languages (Milroy & Muysken, 1995).

According to Poplack (2000) there are different types of Code-switching existing among the speech of multilingual people three are the most prominent: tag switching, inter-sentential switching and intra-sentential switching. The first type relates to the enclosure of one phrase into another language. The second type includes switching at clause or sentence level. Romaine, (1989) highlighted that inter-sentential code-switching needs mastery of both the languages. The third type is of switching within the sentences. Apart from these three basic types Gumpers (1982) extends it to situational and metaphorical level of language. The first one depends upon members or schemes, whereas later depends upon the contemporary prominence. In metaphorical CS language determines the situation.

From the psychological perspective, Bullock and Toribio (2009) mention that it is not a language disorder rather it is proficiency of bi and multilingual speakers. Paul (2007) defines the language disorder as that it is a deficiency of the speaker during conversation, understanding or can be related to any other aspect of language appropriateness. It is not a mental disorder because when a person is fully

exposed to two different languages it is unavoidable for him/her not to utilize them both at a same time.

Rolin and Brownlie (2002) investigated four high school classes and developed an argument that L1 is helpful for enhancing the comprehension level of students regarding the new input of TL. Jingxia's (2010) research on teachers' Code-Switching reveals that CS in academic setting has positive impact upon students learning outcomes. Similarly Yao, (2011) favored the use of Code-Switching. Rezvani (2011) investigation of EFL classrooms which shows the positive effect of CS in classroom as it helps learners to reach the goal of education. Dweik (2000), points out that bilingualism is major cause in linguistics and culture interference and suggests that use of first language in the classroom setting can create interference at phonological level and cultural level.

In Pakistan majority people use mix languages which are known as multilingual or bilinguals. Pakistan is a state where people use many languages in their daily communication, thus code-switching is the major act performed by the Pakistani speakers who communicate in different environments, i.e. work place, families, educational institutions etc.

Methodology

Research Questions

The research questions of the present study are as under:

1. What are the differences in students' attitudes towards the teachers' use of CS on gender at undergraduate level?
2. What are the differences in attitudes regarding teachers' CS on the basis of natural and social science programs?
3. What are the variations in attitudes regarding CS on the basis of students' academic background?

Communication Accommodation Theory

The present study applied Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT). It is introduced by Giles (2008), who pursues to describe the cognitive reasons for Code-Switching, and other changes in speech, where a person either highlights or reduces the social differences between himself and the other person(s) during the daily discourse. When speakers want an approval in a social situation, they prefer to link their speech with that of the other speaker. It depends on the language of choice, accent, dialect, and para-linguistic features which usually participants used in the daily discourse. On the other hand, the speakers can priorities the linguistic

features of their own group to highlight the social distance between him and other speakers.

Research Design

The population of this study comprised of the students enrolled in Undergraduate programs of Natural and Social sciences departments at the universities of federal government. To provide an equal chance of selection to every individual of the population a simple Random sampling applied to draw representative sample for the study.

A questionnaire was adapted from El-Fiki (1999) to investigate attitudes of students. The questionnaire is aimed to focus on the following areas relating classroom setting; CSD (Code-Switching a disadvantage), CSA (Code-Switching as an Advantage), CSTM (Code-Switching as a Teaching Methodology). The SPSS software is used, and reliability analysis was conducted separately for each items of questionnaire (i.e., DCS, ACS and CSTM) and it was .747, .715 and .704 respectively. The data was first comprised of more than 500 responses but after treating the missing values (through Mahalanobis missing analysis), the reliable data remained 443. Independent Sample T-test and One-way ANOVA has been used for analysis.

Results

Attitudes of Students regarding Code-Switching on Gender Basis

The students' attitudes were investigated on gender basis. For this purpose, an independent sample t-test was conducted in three directions. The compute variable was calculated. A compute variable is a mean value of multiple variables, which belong to one dimension. These three directions were, Advantages of CS (ACS), Disadvantages of CS (DCS) and CS used as helping hand in teaching methodology (CSTM).

Table 1. Analysis of CSD based on Gender

	Male	Female			95% CI	
	<i>n=190</i>	<i>n=253</i>			LL	UL
Variables	M(SD)	M(SD)	t(443)	P	LL	UL
DCS	3.03(0.670)	3.28(0.698)	-3.72	0.000	-0.37496	-0.11591

Df=441

An independent-sample t-test was performed against gender to find out students' attitude towards CS inside the classroom. On gender basis statistical data show a

significant difference in the attitudes of students towards the disadvantages of CS (CSD) among males and females. Males ($M=3.03$, $SD= .67$) and Females ($M=3.2841$, $SD= .69854$); $t(443) = -3.724$, $p= .000$ (two tailed) indicates a significant difference as shown in Table 1.

Table 2. Analysis of CSTM based of Gender

Variables	Male	Female	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	n= 190	n= 253			LL	UL
	M(SD)	M(SD)				
CSTM	2.11(.50)	2.20(.55)	-1.66	.096	-.185	.015

Df= 441

Note: CSTM= Code Switching as a helping hand in Teaching Methodology

The test was conducted for investigating attitudes of students for the advantages of CS inside the classroom. There was significant difference in statistical scores of students on the basis of gender. Males ($M=2.21$ $SD=.48$), Females ($M=2.36$ $SD=.47$); $t(443) = -3.34$, $p= .001$ (two tailed) is significant.

Table 3. Analysis of CSTM based of Gender

Variables	Male	Female	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	n= 190	n= 253			LL	UL
	M(SD)	M(SD)				
ACS	2.21(.48)	2.36(.47)	-3.34	.001	-.244	-.063

Df= 441

The test was carried out to compare the attitudes of Students towards teachers CS inside the classroom on the basis of gender and program. No significant difference in statistical scores was noticed for both the programs' students on the basis of gender. Males ($M=2.11$ $SD=.50$), Females ($M=2.20$ $SD=.55$); $t(443) = -1.66$, $p= .096$ (two tailed) is not significant.

Attitudes of Students regarding Code-Switching on the basis of Social and Natural Sciences

The attitudes of Social and Natural science students towards the teachers' use of CS were investigated. The main purpose of investigation is to figure out the existence of any difference in the attitudes of Social and Natural science students towards teachers' use of CS inside the classroom. In order to perform the investigation independent sample t-test is used in three directions that are Advantages of CS (ACS), Disadvantages of CS (DCS) and CS used as helping hand in teaching methodology (CSTM). The result of t-test showed in the table below:

Table 4. Analysis of CSD on the basis of Program

Variables	SS	NS	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	n= 252	n= 191			LL	UL
	M(SD)	M(SD)				
CSD	3.09(.656)	3.28(.734)	-2.80	.005	-.316	-.055

Df= 441

Note: CSD= Code Switching Disadvantages CI= Confidence Interval; LL= Lower Limit; UL= Upper Limit

In the above table the *p* value shows that there is a significant difference regarding disadvantages of CS based on program. Social Science students (M=3.09, SD= .65) and Natural Science Students (M=3.28, SD= .73); t (443) = -2.805, *p*= .005 (two tailed) also indicates a significant difference.

Table 5. Analysis of CSA on the basis of Program

Variables	SS	NS	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	n= 252	n= 191			LL	UL
	M(SD)	M(SD)				
ACS	2.36(.47)	2.21(.48)	3.16	.002	.055	.236

Df= 441

Note: ACS= Advantages of Code Switching

Social Science (M=2.36 SD=.47), Natural Science (M=2.21 SD=.48); t (443) = 3.16, *p*= .002 (two tailed) is also significant. The above mentioned significant values shed light upon the area that ACS has a remarkable influence on

program the mean difference shows that the attitude of Social science students differs from that of the natural science students. Hence, Social science students have more DCS towards CS than Natural science students.

Table 6: Analysis of CSTM on the basis of Program

Variables	SS n= 252	NS n= 191	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	M(SD)	M(SD)			LL	UL
CSTM	2.16(.531)	2.15(.538)	.168	.867	-.092	.109

Df= 441

Note: CSTM= Code Switching as a helping hand in Teaching Methodology

Social Science (M=2.11 SD=.505), Natural Science (M=2.20 SD=.551); $t(443) = -1.66$ $p = .096$ (two tailed) is significant. The above-mentioned significant values shed light upon the area that CSTM influence program. The mean difference shows that the attitude of Social science students differs from that of the natural science students regarding CSTM.

Table 7: Analysis of CSTM on the basis of Secondary Educational Background

Variables	P n= 266	G n= 176	t(443)	P	95% CI	
	M(SD)	M(SD)			LL	UL
CSTM	2.10(.517)	2.24(.537)	-2.58	.010	-.231	-.031

Df= 440

Note: CSTM= Code Switching as helping hand in Teaching Methodology

There was significant difference in statistical scores for students on the base of academic background i.e. Private or Government at secondary level. Private (M=2.10 SD=.517), Government (M=2.24 SD=.537); $t(443) = -2.58$, $p = .010$ (two tailed) is significant. The mean difference shows that the attitude towards CS as a helping hand in teaching methodology; of those students who has private academic background are different from the attitudes towards CS as a helping hand in teaching methodology; of students who has Government academic background.

Table 8: Analysis of DCS based on Medium of Instruction use at Primary level

Descriptive							
DCS							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% CI LL	UL	MinimumMaximum
Urdu	100	3.1087	.70782	.07078	2.9683	3.2492	1.38 4.88
English	214	3.1389	.70419	.04814	3.0441	3.2338	1.25 5.00
Urdu and English	129	3.2994	.66403	.05846	3.1837	3.4151	1.75 5.00
Total	443	3.1789	.69642	.03309	3.1138	3.2439	1.25 5.00

ANOVA

DCS					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.*
Between Groups	2.708	2	1.354	2.814	.061
Within Groups	211.663	440	.481		
Total	214.371	442			

* Significant level is at 0.10 (90% CI)

The ANOVA test is conducted in order to investigate any difference of the impact of medium of instruction on the attitudes of students towards the disadvantages of CS use by the teachers. The three medium use in general as medium of instruction i.e. Urdu, English and Urdu & English together. The ratios of students for these mediums were different as Urdu 100, English 214 and Urdu & English 129. The result shows a slightly significant difference i.e. $p = .061$ (two tailed).

Table 9: Analysis of ACS based on Medium of Instruction use at Primary level

Descriptive							
ACS							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% CI LL	UL	MinimumMaximum
Urdu	100	2.1725	.49405	.04941	2.0745	2.2706	1.00 3.40
English	214	2.3319	.48990	.03349	2.2659	2.3979	1.00 3.60
Urdu and English	129	2.3484	.45586	.04014	2.2689	2.4278	1.10 3.40
Total	443	2.3007	.48514	.02305	2.2554	2.3460	1.00 3.60

ANOVA

ACS					
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	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.144	2	1.072	4.630	.010*
Within Groups	101.884	440	.232		
Total	104.029	442			

* Significant level is at 0.10 (90%)

The ANOVA test is run in order to explore any difference of the impact of medium of instruction (at primary level) on the attitudes of students towards the advantages of CS use by the teachers. The three medium use in general as medium of instruction i.e. Urdu, English and Urdu & English together. The ratios of students for these mediums were different as Urdu 100, English 214 and Urdu & English 129. The result shows a slightly significant difference i.e. $p = .010$ (two tailed).

Qualitative Analysis

A qualitative study was also conducted through open-ended question given at the end of survey questionnaire. The researcher recorded different opinion of the students. According to the undergraduate university students CS is an important tool for teaching in Pakistan. Most of the students favor the practice of CS inside the classroom. Therefore the opinions recorded in the favor of CS use. Out of 443 questionnaires only 102 students respond to the open ended question.

Table 10. Themes Derived from Comments

Codes No.		No. of Comments
C1	Diverse linguistic background	7
C2	Diverse academic background	16
C3	CS Practice in Teaching	20
C4	Concept clarification	37
C5	Communication in real life situation	5
C6	CS motivational tool for students	6
C7	Debate between national and international language	9
C8	CS is a universal phenomenon	2
	Total	102

The qualitative remarks were analyzed in the light of socio-educational features, which help the learning and teaching environment. The students were asked to share their remarks by keeping in view their experiences inside the classroom. The qualitative remarks given by the students, give emersion to different ideas, where

the CS practice could be helpful. The reasons in the view point of students due to which teachers use CS or they should use CS are as above.

Discussion

This research sets out to look at the students' attitudes towards the use of "Code-Switching" by the teachers based on their classroom experiences at undergraduate level in Pakistan. The study further examined the practice of Code Switching favored by the students or not. The findings of the current research witnessed the relationship between code switching use by the Pakistani teachers and attitudes of Pakistani students towards its use inside the classroom. Furthermore, the research analyzed the effect of different variables (such as gender, Natural and social science program, Primary and secondary education was from private or government school and medium of instruction at the school level) on attitudes towards CS use by the teachers inside the classroom.

Attitudes of Students regarding Code-Switching on Gender Basis

According to the result of independent sample t-test there is a significant difference with a 95% of confidence interval. This shows that the attitudes of males are different as compared to females towards the teachers' use of CS. According to Cheshire and Gardner-Chloros (1998) CS is considered as nonstandard form of speech, and the results of their study shed light on the scenario that woman use more standard form than man to bilingual code-switched data. Their study also indicated that there is a remarkable gender difference in the attitudes of males and females towards the use of CS. However, this study was conducted out of the academic setting. Another study by Asghar, Abusaeedi, and Jafarian (2016) shows that gender has no impact on students' attitudes towards teachers' use of CS. As contrary to this the result of current study shows a significant difference on the basis of gender. As the p value in the result of my study (i.e. $p = .000$) shows that there is a gender difference in the attitudes of students towards the teacher use of CS.

As three compute variables were calculated in order to run t-test. The compute variable is a mean value of multiple variables which belong to one dimension. These three directions were, Disadvantages of CS (CSD), Advantages of CS (CSA) and CS used as helping tool in teaching methodology (CSTM). The result of CSD showed the statistical difference in terms of gender. This indicates that male students' negative attitudes (towards teachers' use of CS) are different as compared to female students. The difference is shown by the significant value of two tailed i.e. $p = .000$ (As sig. value must be less than $p = .05$). Similarly, the difference is seen in the negative attitudes of students towards teachers' use of CS

on gender basis. The statistical result of independent sample t-test has given the value $p = .001$ which highlights the difference in two groups i.e. male and female students. The data for analysis gathered from the federal Universities of Pakistan, although Islamabad is the capital of Pakistan. However, Pakistan is considered as a patriarchal state where male dominance is obvious. The upbringing of females never let them to express their feelings explicitly. Moreover, females' exposure to the world is less as compared to males but this can't be generalized to all contexts. The result of current study shows the difference on the basis of gender where male and female have different attitudes towards the language use. As CS is considered as a more polite and informal form of speech, therefore it enhances the learning process. Moreover, it can help in student teacher relationship which in turn will boost up the learning process.

However, the use of CS in academic setting is an acceptable style of speech for students as the result shows no difference in CS as a helping tool in teaching method on the basis of gender. Both male and female accept CS as a helping tool in teaching method as the mean value of both the groups shows their opinion towards the agreement on a five point Liked scale. There is no significant difference on 95% confidence interval in the attitudes of students towards the idea that CS serves as a helping tool in teaching methodology. The result has given the $p = .096$ which indicates no significant difference in two groups i.e. male and female in terms of their attitudes towards CS as a helping tool in teaching methodology.

Attitudes of Students regarding Code-Switching on the basis of Social and Natural Sciences

According to the result of independent sample t-test there is a significant difference with a 95% of confidence interval. This shows that the attitude of students towards the teachers' use of CS is different on the basis of program i.e. Social science and Natural science. The previous studies in the chapter of literature review highlight the fact that teachers and students who are exposed to two different language use CS inside the classroom. However, the attitudes of social science students are different from the natural science students. In the result of t-test the p -value indicates the difference as $p = .005$ which points out that the attitudes of social and natural science students towards teachers' use of CS in terms of its disadvantages has a significant difference. The opinion of both the groups is different on the basis of the program they are enrolled in. Although both the program students need to understand the concept in order to get the gist of the particular subject they are studying. But the difference in attitudes could be on the basis of their approach towards the language use by the teachers inside the classroom. As the natural science students are more concerned about the bookish language, they are restricted scientifically to different experiments and procedures. As compared to this social science students are free to the real world situations. For social science

students the society and culture is the real concern. Hence, they aren't bound to the bookish or scientific language. Moreover, social science students mostly study about the people and their way of living and for them students main purpose of language is to communicate. For both the program students the attitudes towards disadvantages of CS i.e. CSD showed a significant difference.

Similarly, the significant difference can be seen in their attitudes towards the advantages of CS use by the teachers inside the classroom. The difference can be seen in the result with the 95 % confidence interval where the two tailed significant value is $p = .002$ which indicate a clear difference. Both the program students can have this difference due to their discipline related course content. As social science students has to interact with the real life society more rather than the natural science students. Natural science students are restricted to the labs doing experiments on the other hand social science students research while living and interacting the real life society.

Attitudes based on Education Private/Government at Secondary level

The one group of private and government tested with the other group of three-compute variable through independent sample t-test. The result shows that on secondary level there is no significant difference in the attitude of students towards teachers' use of CS in terms of advantages and disadvantages of CS. The reason could be the same as the data taken from the undergraduate university student of 2016. Therefore, at their time of secondary education there was no much difference between private and government school. The $p = .426$ for CSD and the $p = .711$ shows that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of students on the basis of their secondary education. However, the $p = .010$ for CSTM shows a significant difference in the attitudes of students. The students' attitudes differ for the perspective of CS use as a helping tool in teaching methodology on the basis of secondary education. With confidence interval of 95 % it could be said as the attitudes of students who has secondary education from private school system is different from the attitudes of those who came from government school system.

Attitudes based on Medium of instruction used at Primary Level

In the test result of ANOVA the total number of students who use Urdu as their medium of instruction at primary level are 100. The students who experience English as a language of instruction at primary level are 214. Moreover, students who experience Urdu & English together as a medium of instruction at primary level are 129. Although there is no significant difference with the 95 % of confidence interval but if the confidence interval is taken as 90% then it could be said as there is a significant difference as the $p = .061$ which is significant for the

students attitudes towards the advantages of CS use by the teachers in the classroom.

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The qualitative analysis of the remarks given by the students in the open-ended question elucidates the relationship of students with teachers regarding the use of CS inside the classroom in Pakistan. Moreover, it also reveals the advantages of CS use between both languages (i.e. the students' local language, Urdu and institutional language, English) in teaching different disciplines.

The qualitative analysis regarding the CS use discloses that it is a strong support in understanding the subject related complex concepts. However, sole focus on the use of one language can create a fuss inside the classroom. As Pakistani students have diverse linguistic and academic background. Using one-language can result in lack of interest towards the course in which the students are enrolled in. To avoid such fuss there is a need to use CS. In Pakistan, the textbooks that are used in educational institutes, are edited by foreign textbook authors mostly and are entirely in English language. As a result of that students are often find it difficult to comprehend the concepts. In order to help the students, teachers should act as a bridge and play the role of link between textbook and the students.

The analysis figure out that the students' native language is important. It discloses the phenomenon that students find themselves motivated to learn the concepts of their subjects by the use of local language. The major factor which triggers their motivational level is the supremacy of their local language. Moreover, Pakistani teachers and students mostly share the same language. Mostly the teachers also prefer to use local language in order to clarify the concept of the particular discipline. The analysis also suggests that discipline related concept can

be clarified if the teachers modify the concepts found in textbooks with the examples related to the region.

The analysis in general suggests a balance between the students' local language i.e. Urdu and the institutional language i.e. English. Hence, teaching which includes the practice of CS is helpful as it enables the students aware about the concepts. In concerning with this it is suggested that teachers should be witty enough to know when and how they'll have to use CS. Moreover they should have full command on both the languages i.e. Urdu and English.

The research study also highlights the importance of CS as it is not restricted to any particular two languages. CS is a universal phenomenon and it could be applicable in any of two or more languages not only between Urdu and English. The qualitative analysis rely on students' remarks put forward the idea that learning can be make easy through CS use by the teachers. Teaching which includes CS practice enables the students to have a direct contact with the concepts and to have comprehensive approach regarding their course in which they are supposed to be graduated.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the teachers and students both are engaged in the practice of CS. As teachers use CS so the students have different attitudes towards its use. The current study is first of its kind attempting to uncover Pakistani students' attitudes towards teachers' use of CS. It has provided empirical evidence regarding the difference in attitudes of students on the basis of gender, program and educational background. The study has also highlighted the attitudes of students towards the reasons due to which students think that their teachers use CS. The findings shed light on the significant difference in students' attitude. The findings meet the objectives of the current research.

According to the findings there is a significant difference in the attitudes of students towards teachers' use of CS on the basis of gender and program (i.e. Social and Natural science). However, a slightly significant difference is seen in the attitudes of students towards teachers' use of CS on the basis of academic background. In academic background two things are consider for analysis of students attitudes. One was their primary and secondary level of education, either its private or government and the second one is the medium of instruction that is used in both primary and secondary level of education. On the basis of real life context as in Pakistani scenario three mediums are used for instruction in schools which are Urdu, English and Urdu & English together.

The findings concluded that it doesn't matter if the primary and secondary education is from private or government. The attitudes of students towards teachers' use of CS do not depend on their academic background. However, the medium of instruction does influence the attitudes of students towards teachers'

use of CS. Similarly, the attitudes of students towards the reasons due to which they think their teachers' use CS have significant difference on the basis of gender and program. However, there is no significant difference in their schooling (either its private or government). But the medium of instruction shows a significant difference in their attitudes towards reasons for CS use by the teachers.

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